

CURRENT LEVELS OF DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNET TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING LANGUAGES

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Abstract

The current level of development of Internet technologies and multimedia opens up broad prospects for methods of teaching languages. Using the Web to communicate with native speakers of the target language, exchange information, watch films and programs in the Russian language, including online, becomes an integral part of the educational process and the student's daily life. The purpose of the article is to identify the most effective ways to increase the effectiveness of the Russian language lessons.

Keywords: *target language, exchange information, films, programs, online, educational process, authentic resources, language environment, multicultural education.*

Skillful organization of student interaction based on educational material becomes a powerful factor in increasing the effectiveness of educational activities as a whole [10]. The relevance of the above is determined not only by social order, but also by a person's needs for self-determination and self-expression in the conditions of a modern, information society. The process of Uzbekistan's entry into the international educational space is becoming more and more energetic, and in connection with this, the question of finding an optimal match between established traditions in domestic higher education and new trends arises. The "new" trends included in the State Standard for Foreign Languages in institutions are an expanded range of competencies in intercultural communication [1].

A new stage of education can be called awareness of the national education system. Modern technologies are used to develop self-education skills. Students have a desire to use the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities, not only in an educational institution, but also in real life, outside the institute walls.

The most detailed definition of this concept is given by I.V. Robert [9]. By “informatization of education” the researcher understands a purposefully organized process of providing the education sector with methodology, technology and practice of creating and optimally using scientific, pedagogical, educational and methodological developments focused on realizing the capabilities of information and communication technologies (ICT) used in comfortable and health-preserving environments [2].

Nowadays, students are born into the modern digital world, which is full of innovative technologies and ideas.

Students now have the opportunity to receive educational material remotely; this delivery of material is more interesting for modern students and is also convenient.

The Internet is full of useful information. It allows students to develop “without boundaries” with great interest. Students use information not only from various electronic libraries (which is very convenient for self-development), but also to write various essays, reports, etc.

Scientists divide software as follows [3]:

1. By the method of presenting information. There are several of these methods. These include multimedia technologies, text and hypertext.
2. By functional value: various simulators, electronic textbooks and books, testing programs, etc.

The current level of development of Internet technologies and multimedia opens up broad prospects for methods of teaching languages [4]. Using the Web to communicate with native speakers of the target language, exchange information, watch films and programs in the Russian language, including online, becomes an integral part of the educational process and the student’s daily life. The Internet provides a unique opportunity for the Russian language teacher to use modern authentic resources, immersing students in an authentic language environment, and is a prerequisite for organizing linguistic multicultural education [5].

As a source of additional materials for teachers in preparation for lessons. Various materials are presented in both printed and electronic form. But, unfortunately, in this case only part of the Internet's capabilities are realized. Students can use the network

themselves for educational purposes. Conducting a lesson using Internet technologies can have different purposes [6]: searching for information, answering a question, preparing for a project, creating a personal page or website. By installing various programs on the computer, such as skype, zoom, msn and others, students can communicate with peers online. Thus, by adding Internet resources to the educational process, the teacher is able to more effectively solve a number of didactic tasks, such as [7]:

- develop reading skills and abilities using online materials of varying degrees of complexity;
- improve the skills of monologue and dialogic oral speech;
- replenish active and passive vocabulary with vocabulary of the modern Russian language;
- get acquainted with cultural knowledge, including speech etiquette, features of the speech behavior of various peoples in communication conditions, features of the culture and traditions of the country of the language being studied.

Thus, today, informatization of education is one of the goals that the state sets for educational institutions. Information and communication technologies are actively being introduced into the educational process to expand knowledge and develop a number of competencies [8].

With the adoption of the new law on education and the release of federal state educational standards, the process of reorienting Uzbek education began from a “knowledge-based” approach to a competency-based approach, implying the formation in students not so much of certain skills and abilities, but rather of relevant competencies, the possession of a combination of which allows us to say that students have that or other competence.

The role of ICT in teaching the Russian language can hardly be overestimated; they have great information and educational potential. Nowadays, informatization of education is one of the goals that the state sets for educational institutions. Information and communication technologies are actively being introduced into the educational process to expand knowledge and develop a number of competencies. The most popular ICT tools remain the computer and the Internet, which, in turn, is our second

habitat and a source of authentic information. All this allows us to assert that these technologies and Internet resources contribute to the formation of key competencies, and, consequently, the implementation of the main goal of teaching the Russian language in institute.

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